

THE EFFECT OF INTERFACE BONDING STRENGTH OF C/Al
COMPOSITES ON TENSILE STRENGTH
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ABSTRACT

A method of measuring the interface bonding strength of C/Al composite precursor wires and the effect on the tensile strength have been studied in this paper. We also provide a self made small scale shear testing machine to measure the longitudinal shear strength of composite wires. The interface bonding strength was expressed by converting the longitudinal shear strength of composite wire through calculation. Generally, interface shear strength is equal to the longitudinal shear strength multiplied by the coefficient of $2/\gamma$. It is found in the experiment that the interface shear strength between fiber and matrix of composite wire can be estimated by the means of measuring the longitudinal shear strength of composite wire. In certain interface shear strength range the tensile strength of composite wire has a inversely proportional of interface shear strength .

KEYWORDS: Composites; Shear strength; Interface bonding strength; Tensile strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

The effect of interface bonding states on the tensile strength of composite is a noticeable problem. Many authors have worked on this topic but the results were varied. This is because the effect of interface bonding are varied with the different properties of matrices and fibers, Since C/Al metal matrix composite is one of the useful materials, so that it is necessary to study the effect of interface bonding strength on tensile strength of such composite. We find the bonding strength of original composite plate produced by hot press is too high, so that it is hardly to change its bonding strength by futher treatment. However the interface bonding of composite wire is in a moderate state since the infiltrated time with fiber into aluminum is short and some methods can be used to change its bonding. So

using composite wire as specimens is feasible to study the effect of interface bonding on their tensile strength. Limited by the dimension of composite wires, one can't use conventional testing method to measure the bonding strength. Although some measuring methods are suggested in literature such as fiber pull out from the its matrix, but it usually failed since the fiber is easily broken down during testing. Some authors did it by calculating the number and length of fiber pull out in a certain areas found in the tensile fracture surface of specimens. But the data from partial areas are not always reliable. In this work we measure longitudinal shear strength of composite wire by a special design machine and then estimate the interface shear strength through calculation method. This test is desirable in the experiment and reliable on data analysis.

2. SPECIMENS AND TESTING METHODS

The specimens used in this work were different kinds of C/Al composite wires fabricated by means of CVD to form Ti-B coating on the surface of fiber and then infiltrated with molted aluminum. Fibers were T300 and M40 from Japan and high strength carbon fiber Cs made in Shanghai. Matrix were pure aluminum as well as LD2,LD10,LC4 and Al-Ti aluminum alloy.

Since the diameter of wire is only 0.5 mm, considering the stability of specimens during shear testing. Two millimetre in length is suitable. In order to measure shear strength of this kind of composite wire, we design a special shear testing machine as shown on Fig.1. Fig.2 shows the way of specimens place and the form of load apply schematically. The edge of up and down knives put on two half cross section of specimens. Since fixture and down knife move up together, it can prevent friction between fixture and specimen. While the up edge of knife is fixed, it makes specimens shear fracture in longitudinal direction parallel to fiber. The load value P which pushing fixture and down knife up is measured by model BLR-10 force transducer. The shear fracture section areas were measured by microscopy. The shear strength τ is the load P divided by section area S.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Shear Fracture Feature of Composite Wires Using shear strength testing machine to measure shear strength of different kinds of composite wires, Shear fracture section investigated by SEM was shown on figure 3. The feature of shear surface could be divided into three kinds of modes.

1. shear surface in week interface bonding shown in figure 3(b) . The feature of this surface is uneven. There are many bare fibers in surface layer of shear section and no matrix on the fiber surface, shear fracture basically

Figure 1. Small shear strength testing machine

Figure 2. The form of load apply in shear testing

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 3. Shear fracture sections of C/Al composite wires investigated by SEM (a) macroscopic shape (b) weak interface bonding (c) moderate interface bonding (d) strong interface bonding

occured in the interface between fiber and matrix and matrix didn't endure shear load. 2. shear surface in moderate interface bonding strength shown in figure 3.(c). Shear surface also was consist of bare fiber only on the surface layer, but it is evidence that some of residue matrix adhere to the fiber surface. The shear fracture was partially due to the interface shear fracture. Matrix didn't endure shear strength mainly. 3. shear surface in strong interface bonding is shown in figure 3 (d). That is the matrix shear fracture surface and shear fracture occured in matrix.

3.2 The Expressing Way for Interface Shear Strength Suppose the distribution of the fiber in composite wire is in uniform as shown in figure 4. The nearest distance between any two fibers surface is presented by q . The size of distance q depends on fiber volume fraction. Connect the centre of three fibers to form a triangle as a unit and the ratio of the area of parts of fibers in this triangle $S_{f\Delta}$ to the area of triangle S_{Δ} is fiber volume fraction, as following relation:

$$S_{f\Delta} / S_{\Delta} = V_f \tag{1}$$

let the radius of fiber is r , $S_{f\Delta}$ and S_{Δ} can be obtained by

$$S_{f\Delta} = \frac{1}{2} \pi r^2 \tag{2}$$

$$S_{\Delta} = \frac{3}{4} (2r+q)^2 \tag{3}$$

if the radius of composite wire is R , and the fiber is 3000 filaments per tow, then fiber volume fraction V_f can be deduced by following equation:

$$V_f = 3000 \cdot \pi r^2 / \pi R^2 \tag{4}$$

Figure 4. The distribution form of fibers in composite wires

Figure 5. Ideal shear section of composite wires

Substitute equation (2), (3), (4) into equation (1), when the fiber radius r is $3.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}$ and the composite wire diameter $2R$ is 0.5mm , so the nearest distance q between two fibers surface is $1.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}$.

Shear section of composite wire is situated in the section which pass through

the centre of fiber shown as in figure 5. Firstly, the possibility of shear section situated in matrix is not large. The largest distance Q of matrix section without any fibers can be obtained by following equation

$$Q = \frac{3}{4} (2r+q) - 2r \quad (5)$$

Substitute known data in equation (5), $Q=0.44 \times 10^{-6} m$, compared with fiber diameter this distance Q is much smaller. So even if the interface shear strength is close to matrix shear strength, the possibility of shear fracture occurred in matrix is small. Secondly interface shear strength is smaller than that of matrix, it means shear fracture is easily occurred in the interface to get the largest interface areas and smallest matrix areas. Whole shear section areas consist of semicircle areas of fiber surface S_1 and matrix area S_2 , when the width of shear section is D , The number of fiber in the section within the width D is n , following equation can be given:

$$n = \frac{D}{2r + q} \quad (6)$$

$$S_1 = nh \pi r \quad (7)$$

$$S_2 = nhq \quad (8)$$

In this equations, h is length of shear section, the whole shear load of composite wire is equal to the shear load of the interface add to the shear load of the matrix, That is

$$P = \tau_f S_1 + \tau_m S_2 \quad (9)$$

So the interface shear strength τ_f is given by

$$\tau_f = \frac{P - \tau_m nhq}{nh \pi r} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) is deduced on the base of three suppositions, they are fiber distribution is uniform, shear section pass though the centre of fiber and whole shear load of composite wire is equal to one of the interface add to one of the matrix section. In fact, the fiber distribution is not uniform, there are some fibers closed to each other in certain areas, and shear fracture is easily occurred near these closed fibers. Shear fracture section is not certainly in the one layer, but always several layers combined with some closed fiber sections. In the meanwhile matrix almost has no contribution to shear strength of composite wires. So it is necessary to modify equation (10). That is without considering the contribution of matrix shear strength to calculate the number of fibers in the section within the width D according to the fact that fiber is closed each other. So the interface shear strength can be given by:

$$\tau_f = \frac{P}{nh \pi r} = \frac{2}{\pi} \cdot \frac{P}{S} = \frac{2}{\pi} \tau_c \quad (11)$$

in this equation P is the load from testing. S is shear section area and τ_c is shear strength of composite wire.

3.3 The Relationship between Tensile Strength and Interface Shear Strength

According to the supposition of equation (11), shear strength from the calculated result of equation is closed to interface shear strength in second mode of shear section. Because this supposition is closed to actually shear states, and second mode of shear section is the one of large parts of composite wire, so equation (11) is suitable. In first mode of shear section, shear strength from equation (11) is larger than that from reality, because the actual area of first mode of shear section is larger than that used in calculation. However equation (11) is not suitable for third mode of shear section. Actually, interface shear strength in this kind of composite wire can't be obtained by this method of longitudinal shear testing, but undoubtedly its interface bonding strength is larger than shear strength of matrix.

Figure 6. The interface shear strength and tensile strength of Cs/LD₂ composite wires after heat treatment for one hour

The shear strength of composite wires for different aluminum alloys matrix and after different kinds of treatment had been obtained according to the calculated result from equation (11) as shown in figure 6,7,8. Compared with their tensile strength, it is found that the tensile strength of composite wire is inverse proportional to interface shear strength. The interface

Figure 7. The interface shear strength and tensile strength of T300 fiber different aluminum alloys matrix composite wires

Figure 8. The interface shear strength and tensile strength of M40/LD₂ composite wires after different times of thermal cycling

shear strength of T300/LC₄ and T300/LD₁₀ are the highest while the tensile strength is lowest, and the contrast is very obvious. The interface shear strength of M40/LD₂ composite wire in original state is higher, after thermal cucling, interface bonding is slaked by thermal stress and shear strength become lower, the shear strength decreased about 45% and tensile strength increased about 57% after ten times of thermal cycling. The relationship between tensile strength and interface bonding strength is very clear. So the interface bonding strength is the most important factor to control the tensile strength of composite.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The interface shear strength between fiber and matrix in composite wires can be estimated by the methods of measuring the longitudinal shear strength of composite wire.
2. The tensile strength of C/Al composite wire has an inversely proportional relation to interface shear strength. In the certain requirement, decreasing the interface shear strength can increase the tensile strength of composite wire.
3. Heat treatment methods can be used to change the interface bonding strength. After higher temperature treatment the interface bonding strength of composite wire may be larger than that of matrix. In this condition shear fracture occurred in the matrix, and the tensile strength of composite wire is very low.

5. REFERENCE

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